

Advanced manufacturing for efficient GDC diffusion barrier layer by rapid thermal processing for large-area solid oxide cells

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HIGHLIGHTS

- GDC diffusion barrier layers fabricated by magnetron sputtering at room temperature.
- RTP is employed for fast-sintering of dense 200 nm-thick GDC layers.
- 30 % performance boost in SOC button cells over porous GDC barrier layer reference.
- Scaling-up on $12 \times 8 \text{ cm}^2$ large-area SOCs for stack measurement in SOFC/SOEC.
- Up to 60 % large-area SOC power output enhancement over the reference.

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ABSTRACT

Solid oxide cells (SOCs) utilizing mixed ionic-electronic conductors often face performance limitations due to undesired reactions with conventional stabilized-zirconia electrolytes. Ceria-based diffusion barrier layers mitigate these reactions, enhancing electrode activity and durability. Recently, physical thin-film methods have enabled sub-micrometer barrier layers with significantly improved performance compared to traditional methods. However, scalability and cost-effectiveness remain key constraints for commercial SOCs. In this work, we developed a gadolinium-doped ceria (GDC) diffusion barrier layer by magnetron sputtering at room temperature, followed by a novel rapid thermal processing (RTP) sintering approach. This method produced a dense submicrometer GDC layer on anode-supported half-cells. Time and energy consumption were significantly reduced compared to conventional processes. Structural, morphological, compositional, and electrochemical characterizations were performed to evaluate quality and performance. Tests on button cells showed >30 % performance improvement over reference cells with state-of-the-art porous barrier layers, with power outputs of 1.26 W cm^{-2} at 0.7 V in fuel cell mode and 1.54 A cm^{-2} at 1.3 V in electrolysis mode at 750 °C. When scaled to large-area cells ($12 \times 8 \text{ cm}^2$) in short stacks, RTP-treated cells achieved up to 60 % improvement in fuel cell and 30 % in electrolysis at 650 °C. This approach provides a viable route for large-scale production of high-performance SOCs.

1. Introduction

The widespread implementation of SOC devices relies on developing robust materials that can endure high temperatures and harsh conditions while maintaining long-term performance [1,2]. Key components

of state-of-the-art SOCs include a dense yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) electrolyte, a porous Ni-YSZ cermet fuel electrode, and a mixed ionic-electronic oxygen electrode, such as perovskite structures with nominal composition $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{Co}_{1-y}\text{Fe}_y\text{O}_3$ (including $y = 0$) [3], with the latter representing the main bottleneck for the overall cell output and

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stability [4,5]. Compatibility between the electrolyte and the oxygen electrode is essential to obtain high-performance and durable SOCs. Specifically, at the elevated temperatures used during cell fabrication (ca. 1000–1300 °C), cation migration can occur at the interface, leading to the formation of resistive phases, mainly strontium and lanthanum zirconates (SrZrO₃ and La₂Zr₂O₇), hindering oxide ions transport through the electrolyte and causing cell degradation during long-term operation at intermediate temperatures [6–9].

For this reason, diffusion barrier layers are strategically incorporated between these two cell components. Doped ceria oxides are commonly employed for this purpose (e.g. gadolinium or samarium-doped labeled GDC and SDC) due to their high ionic conductivity and good compatibility with YSZ layers [10–12]. The traditional route for barrier layer fabrication entails screen printing followed by high-temperature post-processing for densification. However, residual porosity is often present due to the sintering temperature limit (1200 °C), imposed to prevent massive cationic interdiffusion (e.g. Gd³⁺ and Y³⁺ for GDC-YSZ interface) that would result in unstable interfacial regions [13–15]. Moreover, Sr (from the air electrode) and Zr cations are known to diffuse along preferential pathways of crystallographic (i.e. grain boundaries) and microstructural nature (i.e. pores) leading to SrZrO₃ secondary phase [16].

The density of the barrier layer represents therefore a key parameter for SOC performance [17,18]. Remarkable efforts have been made to develop barrier layers via thin film technology (from micro-to nano-scale) [19,20], as this approach is potentially capable of producing as-deposited layers with higher density. Moreover, thickness minimization is beneficial for reducing the cross-plane device resistance. Among thin-film deposition techniques, electron-beam physical vapor deposition (EB-PVD) [21,22], pulsed laser deposition (PLD) [17,18], and magnetron sputtering [23–25] have been mostly considered in the light of obtaining a high quality of the produced ceramic films. The sputtering method, in particular, is of special interest for scalable industrial production due to the possibility of achieving high film uniformity and large area coverage via low-temperature deposition [26–28].

Previous investigations by the authors have proven that high-temperature post-annealing of GDC protective layers improves the film functionalities due to microstructural evolution (grain growth) [16, 29]. In this regard, RTP emerges as an attractive solution, offering a faster and more energy-efficient alternative to conventional oven treatments [30–33], especially for thin film layers. RTP is an ultrafast infrared light-based technique heating mostly at the surface level with high control over the thermal uniformity across short depths [34], which prevents undesirable phenomena affecting the subsurface, e.g. the degradation or delamination of the fuel electrode due to different thermal expansion of each component [35,36]. Furthermore, rapid thermal treatments can be performed in protective atmosphere, reducing the risk of contamination, degradation or oxidation [37,38].

In this work, we explore the role of rapid thermal processing combined with magnetron sputtering as a fast, energy- and cost-efficient strategy for GDC deposition and treatment, aiming at energy-efficient large-scale cell manufacturing. We present the deposition and complete characterization of a 200 nm-thick GDC barrier layer on reference Ni-YSZ-supported button cells using a low-energy sputtering deposition at room temperature with no voltage bias. This is followed by rapid thermal treatment. The scalability of this approach is demonstrated by extending the process to industrial-size SOCs (12 × 8 cm²). The resulting interlayers are electrochemically evaluated in comparison with similar cells with sputter-produced oven-annealed GDC buffer layers, as well as with reference cells with state-of-the-art screen-printed oven-sintered GDC interlayers. Beyond conventional characterization, a comparative study of the two annealing approaches is conducted using synchrotron-based nano-X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF) [39], providing insight into the chemical composition across the cross-sections of the complete cells, and highlighting the efficacy of the sputtered-RTP-treated barrier layers.

2. Experimental methods

2.1. Cell fabrication

All Ce_{0.8}Gd_{0.2}O_{2.8} barrier layers (≈200 nm thickness) were deposited in a magnetron sputtering equipment (GENCOA, 13.56 MHz) provided with a radiofrequency power generator (BDISCOM). A circular target of 4-inch diameter was used. All films reported in this study were fabricated at a chamber pressure of 0.002 mbar (gas flows: 9 sccm of Ar and 1 sccm of O₂) with no external heating applied to the electrically grounded substrate plate. Deposition power was set at 450 W with a subsequent partial increase of the substrate temperature up to ≈75 °C during the process. The substrate-target distance was 11 cm. The deposition was performed in a static configuration (no substrate holder rotation) with a total deposition time of 45 min at 450 W. For the preliminary electrochemical study, reference Ni-YSZ-supported half-cells from SolydEra S. p.A. were employed. These consisted of a thin YSZ electrolyte (≈8 μm thick) supported by a Ni-YSZ substrate (≈250 μm thick), with 20 mm in diameter. Finally, a scaling-up step involved the use of large-area rectangular Ni-YSZ-supported half-cells (12 × 8 cm²) to test multiple cells in a short stack.

A first set of as-deposited GDC films was fast-sintered using a rapid thermal processor equipment (AS-One 100 system, 30 kW) equipped with a stainless-steel cold wall chamber housing a 100 mm diameter silicon wafer, infrared halogen lamp furnace, optical pyrometers for temperature control and up to 5 process gas lines. The annealing process adopted in this work took place at a chamber pressure of ≈10 mbar after introduction of a gas mixture of O₂ and Ar (gas flows: 42 and 158 sccm, respectively). A preliminary heating ramp with lamp furnace operating at 10 % of the maximum power until the chamber reaches 400 °C for 10 s is used, followed by a fast-heating ramp set at 20 °C/s up to 1150 °C for 6 min after which the temperature is quickly brought down with the same ramp rate resulting in a total process time of ca. 7–8 min. For comparison, a second set of sputtered GDC barrier layers was sintered at the same temperature (1150 °C) for 2 h (2 °C/min ramp rate) in a conventional oven (LENTON) for a total annealing time of ≈21 h. Please note that the target temperature chosen for both annealing methods was previously optimized elsewhere [15] for the same type of materials, using standard laboratory ovens, considering the necessary trade-off between optimum grain growth, film density, and prevention of cations intermixing at the barrier layer/electrolyte interface.

For initial electrochemical characterizations on 8YSZ tapes with the barrier layers sputtered symmetrically on both sides, a porous La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8}O_{3.8} (LSCF6428) cathode ≈15–25 μm-thick was painted on top of each side from a home-made ink prepared using LSCF6428 commercial powder (Fuel Cell Materials) diluted in terpineol in a 1:2 ratio. Painted electrodes were then sintered at 1050 °C for 3 h (3 °C/min). For the complete electrochemical characterization on Ni-YSZ-supported half cells, a two-layer oxygen electrode composed of LSCF-GDC and LSCF6428 was screen-printed on top of the RTP and oven-treated cells and sintered at 1100 °C. A screen-printed LaSrCoO_{3.8} (LSC) top layer was then added to the current collection. The electrode active area is 1.77 cm². A reference cell was also prepared using a ≈2 μm-thick Ce_{0.9}Gd_{0.1}O_{2.8} barrier layer fabricated by standard screen-printing methods and sintered at ≈1300 °C with the rest of the button cell configuration similar to the cells with sputtered GDC barrier layer. A graphical representation of the button cell configurations employed in this work is shown in Fig. S1 of the Supporting Information. After scaling-up to industrial-size cells, the same oxygen electrode and current collector layers were deposited on top of each large-area cell with an electrode active area of 80 cm² per cell. These cells were then combined in a short stack comprised of 5 cells with sputtered barrier layer (three annealed in regular oven and two by fast sintering with RTP) sandwiched between 2 reference cells with screen-printed barrier layers (please refer to Fig. S2 for a schematic representation of the stacking).

2.2. Electrochemical characterization

Complete SOC cells prepared on Ni-YSZ-supported half cells were mounted in a similar ProboStat station (NorECs) placed in a vertical furnace and equipped with a separate compartment on the bottom part for supplementary heating to prevent condensation of water steam during measurements. At the top of the station, where the cell is fixed, gas tightness is achieved using a Ceramabond (Aremco) paste as a gas sealant, separating air and fuel chambers. Au and Ni paste and meshes were used for current collection on the air and fuel electrode side, respectively. The measurements of the complete SOCs were executed at three different working temperatures (800, 750, and 700 °C) in fuel cell mode under dry H₂ fuel and synthetic air, while in electrolysis mode a 90/10H₂O/H₂ fuel composition mix was used for the fuel compartment. An electronic load M9812 (Maynuo Electronic Co. Ltd.) and a power supply LABPS3005D (Velleman) were used to control the current flow and compensate for voltage losses through the cables. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were collected using a PARSTAT 2273 potentiostat operating at open-circuit voltage (OCV) and under cathodic polarization (0.9 V) in fuel cell mode and anodic polarization (1.1 V) in electrolysis mode. Each impedance plot was recorded in galvanostatic mode in the frequency range going from 10⁶ to 0.1 Hz, with an AC amplitude of 50 mA and collecting 10 points each frequency decade. The short stack was electrochemically tested using a testing bench from SolydEra S.p.A. in galvanostatic mode with the maximum current fixed at 33 A in fuel cell mode at three working temperatures: 750, 700, and 650 °C. Gas tightness was ensured by a glass ceramic seal.

2.3. Morphological, structural and compositional analysis

X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were performed by Bruker D8 Advanced diffractometer equipped with a Cu K α radiation source was used and all acquisitions were conducted in the θ – 2θ configuration over a 2-theta range of 20–80°. Atom force microscopy (AFM) by Park System Corp. was used to evaluate GDC film surface morphology after magnetron sputtering deposition for as-deposited, oven- and RTP-annealed barrier layers.

Cross-sectional images of SOC cells after electrochemical measurements were collected using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) equipment provided by Zeiss Auriga to evaluate the cell microstructure and the GDC layer thickness, density, and attachment. To do so, images were acquired using both secondary electrons (SE) for better visualization of morphological features and back-scattered electrons (BSE) for a higher compositional contrast among the different functional layers.

For a deeper understanding of the chemical composition of the studied SOCs and to detect secondary phases around the barrier layer interfaces (e.g. SrZrO₃) at a nanoscale precision, nano-XRF measurements were performed at the ID16B beamline of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) [40]. In preparation for such experiments, thin lamellae were prepared via focused ion beam (FIB) milling from the cross-section of cells embedded in resins and then polished. The so-produced lamellae were 1–2 μm -thick and 20 μm -long with the layers of interest all contained (electrolyte, barrier layer, and oxygen electrode). Please note that small portions of the oxygen electrode might have been removed from the top of the barrier layer during the preparation of the lamellae by FIB milling. The focus area of the x-ray beam was equal to 51 \times 51 nm² (V \times H). Two multi-element Si-drift detectors (3 and 7 elements, 50 mm² of active area each) provided high sensitivity for XRF signal detection. In order to excite the K α , β -XRF lines of zirconium overcoming its threshold and obtaining a clear signal for this element, the x-ray energy was set to 30.5 keV. The scanning area was 7 \times 4 μm^2 using a piezo-motor stage with a step size of 25 \times 25 nm² and accumulation times of 1000 ms. The XRF data were processed using PyMca software to extrapolate a pixel-by-pixel fitting, enabling the generation of intensity maps for each element based on

their characteristic emission lines. This approach provided spatially resolved elemental distributions across the sample.

A thickness-distribution mapping of the GDC on the large-area cells after sputtering was evaluated by spectroscopic ellipsometry prior to electrode deposition and electrochemical testing. The mapping was performed using an ellipsometer from UVISSEL, Horiba scientific in a photon range from 1.45 to 4.4 eV with an interval of 0.07 eV and an integration time of 500 ms. Light beam angle was 70°. Thickness evaluation was performed by fitting the ellipsometry data using DeltaPsi2 software from Horiba scientific. A Tauc-Lorentz dispersion model was adopted to simulate the GDC optical behavior and evaluate the thickness distribution on the cell area.

3. Results and discussion

The performance of solid oxide cells including magnetron sputtered GDC barrier layers were examined in this work under different annealing conditions (conventional oven vs rapid thermal processing). We first focus on the structural and morphological characterization of the GDC film in fuel electrode-supported Ni-YSZ/YSZ/GDC/GDC-LSCF/LSCF button cells.

Fig. 1a reports the XRD patterns for the as-deposited, oven- and RTP-annealed GDC barrier layers. Peaks from the polycrystalline YSZ electrolyte, NiO anode material, and GDC are noted below the diffractograms using cubic-structured references. No secondary peaks were detected for the film as deposited or after each annealing method. Fig. 1b shows a zoom on the main GDC (111) peak. According to ref. [42] the highest intensity GDC (111) reflection appears at 28.48°. For the pristine barrier layer a 0.29° shift towards a lower angle is observed and a progressive shift up to 0.73° towards lower angles occurs across all GDC peaks in the 2θ -range from 20° to 80°. The increasing shifting effect is consistent with the lattice expansion calculated for the as-deposited barrier layer, which has a unit cell \approx 1 % larger than the reference bulk material. Contrarily, GDC films after regular oven-annealing or fast-annealing at 1150 °C exhibit minimal peak shifts (<0.10°) and negligible lattice changes compared to the bulk. The observed lattice expansion is attributed to partial reduction of the ceria (i.e. oxygen deficiency $\delta > 0.1$) [24,41] caused by room temperature sputtering in low oxygen partial pressures. A higher oxygen content is established by air post-annealing with consequent cell volume reduction (5.42 Å). Moreover, both films, after annealing, show narrower and more intense peaks than the as-deposited counterpart, suggesting improved crystallinity from a semi-amorphous thin film typical of layers sputtered at room temperature. A crystallite size calculation using Debye-Scherrer equation [42] was executed. The weighted average value (calculated on the GDC peaks and weighed on each peak intensity contribution) for the pristine GDC is ca. 20 nm which increases to ca. 50 nm for both oven and RTP thermal treatments, giving an estimation of the grain growth and highlighting the effectiveness of rapid annealing to achieve similar structural properties as for standard annealing times. The annealing effect on GDC was also examined using AFM imaging (see Fig. S3 in the Supporting Information), which reveals a smoothing of the film surface morphology on top of the polycrystalline Ni-YSZ substrate as the barrier layer densifies at 1150 °C. The surface root-mean square roughness (R_{ms}) of the sintered cells is comparable for slow and fast annealing by conventional oven and RTP, respectively, with an average value of ca. 21 nm (the high value recorded at 5 \times 5 μm magnification is attributed to YSZ grain boundaries) which is \approx 16 % lower than the pristine film roughness (R_{ms} = 25 nm).

As illustrated in Fig. 2, cross-sectional images by SEM of two Ni-YSZ-supported button cells with sputtered GDC annealed in oven or RTP at high magnification are presented. Please note that these analyses were carried out after electrochemical tests (discussed later in the text) for a proper evaluation of the barrier layer stability. Secondary electron (SE) imaging (Fig. 2a–b) allows to appreciate the morphological features of the GDC thin films highlighting good attachment and uniform coverage

Fig. 1. (a) X-ray diffraction pattern of sputtered GDC barrier layers deposited on Ni-YSZ-supported button cells taken for the as deposited, OVEN-annealed and RTP-annealed cells. Peaks from each XRD pattern are labeled with Miller indices (hkl) from the following reference patterns used for their identification: GDC ($a_{\text{GDC}} = 5.42 \text{ \AA}$ [43]), YSZ ($a_{\text{YSZ}} = 5.14 \text{ \AA}$ [44]) and NiO ($a_{\text{NiO}} = 4.17 \text{ \AA}$ [45]). (b) zoom on the main GDC and YSZ peaks in the 2theta range of 27.5–33.5°.

Fig. 2. SEM cross-sectional images of Ni-YSZ supported cells made of sputtered GDC barrier layers after electrochemical measurements for the button cells with GDC OVEN-annealed (a, c) and RTP-annealed (b, d). In both cases, images are taken using both secondary electron (SE, above) and back-scattered electron detector (BSE, below) for topological and compositional contrast, respectively.

on the electrolyte surface alongside full layer density with no visible pores. Back-scattered electron (BSE) imaging (Fig. 2c–d) reveals higher compositional contrast, enabling a better visualization of the barrier layer thickness (ca. 200 nm) across the film. In contrast, high-magnification SE and BSE images of a reference cell with a screen-printed GDC barrier layer tested in this work is also reported in Fig. S4 displaying pores distributed along the film thickness ($\approx 1.5 \mu\text{m}$). The cross-sectional images of all the cells mentioned also show the porous microstructure of the oxygen electrodes, while indicating the absence of electrode delamination or formation of secondary phases.

Compositional analysis on oven- and RTP-annealed cells was performed by nano-XRF, leveraging synchrotron X-ray radiation with a focused beam to achieve nanometric lateral resolution. The elemental maps of the cross-sections obtained are shown in Fig. 3. Additional data can be found in Fig. S5–7 of the Supporting Information. SEM images of the FIB-prepared lamellae are illustrated in Fig. 3a–c. These images highlight that the SOC area analyzed was centered on the 200 nm-thick

GDC barrier layer (BL), including a portion of the cathode at the top and the electrolyte at the bottom. In Fig. 3b, d one can appreciate the elemental maps acquired from the two cells after GDC sputtering and thermal annealing, followed by deposition and sintering of the porous oxygen electrode on top. These maps were used to investigate potential cation interdiffusion across the tri-layered cross-section examined to assess the presence of secondary phases, such as SrZrO_3 , through cation migration. Mai et al. reported that such a detrimental effect emerges before electrochemical testing, already during the cathode densification at temperatures above $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in relation to the barrier layer quality (e. g. density, grain boundaries distribution) and Sr-content in the cathode (at. %) [46].

Zr-, Ce-, Gd- and Sr-enriched regions displayed here are representative of the electrolyte, barrier layer, and cathode. Given the sharp edges of each elemental distribution, white dashed lines contouring the YSZ/GDC interface were added to simplify the visualization of cation interdiffusion across the protective interlayer. Considering this, the

Fig. 3. SEM images of FIB-prepared lamellae analyzed by nano-XRF of button cells after GDC sputtering and oxygen electrode deposition having (a) OVEN-annealed GDC interlayer and (c) RTP-annealed GDC interlayer. (b) and (d) are the corresponding 2D element mappings for Zr, Ce, Gd, and Sr on the logarithmic scale acquired from their nano-XRF signals. White dashed lines highlight the YSZ/GDC interface.

logarithmic scale of the elemental maps revealed traces of Zr above the dashed lines separating YSZ and GDC for both types of cells, suggesting a cation migration from the electrolyte to the barrier layer. Portions of Sr-rich areas match the Zr-rich spots confirming the presence of restricted regions of SrZrO₃ secondary phase. Bernadet et al. recently reported that a discontinuous formation of strontium zirconate at the interface during cell fabrication at high temperature (≈ 1100 °C) does not affect the electrochemical performances of a Ni-YSZ-supported cell with a 200 nm-thick PLD-produced GDC barrier layer even after 3500 h of testing upon fuel cell conditions [20]. Distribution maps from other cathode elements

(La, Co, and Fe) shown in Fig. S5 did not indicate any other cation migration surpassing the YSZ/GDC interface. Hence, no other secondary phase (e.g. La₂Zr₂O₇) could be detected. Line profiles shown in Figs. S6–7 corresponding to the white vertical lines (labeled I and II) on the elemental maps reveal a sharp transition between Ce and Zr signals. Dark grey regions were marked on the line profile maps to highlight the GDC interlayer based on this clear boundary. For both cells, line profiles labeled as “I” reflect the SrZrO₃ localized presence, highlighting an intensity peak in the Sr signal within the barrier layer. On the other side, line profiles labeled as “II” exemplify the rest of the cell interface’s

chemical nature. The overall condition of the RTP-sintered barrier layer is comparable to the oven-annealed one and for both cross-sections displayed here, isolated zirconate formation (likely at the YSZ grain boundaries) does not affect the electrochemistry of the complete SOC cells (cf. later in the text).

The complete electrochemical analysis on Ni-YSZ-supported button cells with sputtered GDC buffer layers deposited via magnetron sputtering at room temperature is presented in Fig. 4 and in Fig. S8–10 of the Supporting Information. A state-of-the-art bi-layered oxygen electrode (LSCF-GDC/LSCF) was employed for all cells characterized at 800, 750, and 700 °C in both fuel cell (SOFC) and electrolysis (SOEC) mode. Oven- and RTP-sintered cells are compared to a reference cell consisting of a commercially used screen-printed GDC interlayer. In fuel cell conditions, an OCV at around 1.2 V was achieved, as shown in Fig. 4a, indicating proper gas tightness. At 750 °C, the RTP cell achieves a current density of 1.82 A cm⁻² and a power output of 1.26 W cm⁻² at a typical SOFC operating voltage of 0.7 V, representing a remarkable increase of ≈40 % compared to the reference cell (1.30 A cm⁻²; 0.91 W cm⁻²) while performing as effectively as the oven-annealed cell (1.80 A cm⁻²; 1.24 W cm⁻²) at the same operating voltage with low differences within the experimental error. I-V and I-P curves for the oven, RTP, and reference cells acquired at 800 and 700 °C are also shown in Fig. S8a–c highlighting a similar improvement at working voltages of 0.7 V compared to the reference cell at all temperatures. A representative Nyquist plot recorded at 750 °C under 0.9 V bias (c.f. Fig. 4c) was fitted using a simple equivalent circuit comprised of an inductive contribution related to the setup, a serial resistance associated with the current collection and the ionic conductivity of the electrolyte and barrier layer, and finally, a series of 2 RCPE elements for the contribution of the electrodes. The serial resistance contribution for the RTP cell is 0.08 Ω cm⁻², similar to the cell with oven-treated GDC (0.10 Ω cm⁻²) and remarkably lower than the screen-printed reference (0.15 Ω cm⁻²), highlighting a 45 % decrease in ohmic resistance. While a decrease of the serial resistance by implementing a thin-film barrier layer is in principle expected based on literature reports [15,20,24], it should be noted that this result is achieved here also by using ultrafast RTP post-annealing. Wang et al. presented a 1 μm-thick dense GDC buffer layer prepared through arc ion plating (a type of PVD technique) on a Ni-YSZ-supported cell which

gives a significantly higher ohmic contribution at 750 °C (0.19 Ω cm⁻² for the GDC layer sintered at 1100 °C) [47]. Nyquist plots for all cells studied at 800 and 700 °C are presented in Fig. S9a–c. Similarly, in electrolysis mode, at 750 °C and using a H₂O/H₂ fuel composition with a 90/10 ratio (c.f. Fig. 4b), the RTP cell reaches a current density of 1.54 A cm⁻² at the operating voltage of 1.3 V (with maximum current density 1.67 A · cm⁻² recorded at 1.4 V), with an increase of ≈40 % compared to the reference cell (1.11 A cm⁻²) and comparable to the oven-annealed cell at the same conditions (1.70 A cm⁻²). To the best of the authors' knowledge, our findings show high SOEC performances for a Ni-YSZ-supported cell with a thin-film ceria-based barrier layer, which align with studies reported in literature for such a system. Kim et al. reported peak electrolysis current density at around 1.50 A cm⁻² at 800 °C for a similar cell architecture with a 2 μm-thick GDC barrier layer sputtered at 500 °C and sintered at 1100 °C⁴⁸. Coddet et al. achieved an electrolysis current of 1.40 A · cm⁻² recorded at 1.3 V at 800 °C for a Ni-YSZ-supported cell with sputtered GDC barrier layer (<1 μm-thick) annealed at 1100 °C⁴⁹. Molin et al. showed electrolysis current as high as 1.75 A cm⁻² at 1.3 V for a 700 nm-thick barrier layer prepared by spray pyrolysis and sintered at 900 °C⁵⁰. A representative Nyquist plot recorded at 750 °C under 1.1 V bias is shown in Fig. 4d (same fitting circuit as for SOFC, cf. above). I-V curves and Nyquist plots for the sputtered and reference cells are reported in Fig. S8d–f and Fig. S9d–f, respectively.

A summary of the key results for SOCs utilizing dense GDC barrier layers fabricated through thin-film technologies is provided in Table 1. This table compares the performance of the RTP-treated cell investigated in this study with other reported thin-film GDC layers, which were sintered in conventional ovens and tested in both SOFC and SOEC configurations at the button cell level.

According to these results, the RTP-treated cell exhibits comparable performances and properties to the oven-annealed cell, yet with a remarkable improvement in terms of time and energy cost. Consequently, this cell was selected for further durability testing. Fig. 5 summarizes the main results obtained from a preliminary short-term test performed on the cell with RTP-sintered GDC barrier layer. The cell was operated at 750 °C under a cathodic bias of 1 A cm⁻² corresponding to a cell voltage of 0.82 V at t = 0, which increased to 0.83 V after 150 h of

Fig. 4. I-V and I-P curves for the sputtered GDC barrier layers (OVEN-annealed and RTP-annealed) integrated into Ni-YSZ-supported button cells (active area: 1.77 cm²) and measured at 750 °C in comparison with a reference cell composed of a conventional screen-printed GDC buffer layer. Measurements were performed under fuel cell (a) and electrolysis (b) conditions, with Nyquist plots recorded at 0.9 V in SOFC mode (c) and 1.1 V in SOEC mode (d). Gas flows during SOFC analysis were equal to 56 mL min⁻¹ · cm⁻² of H₂ at the fuel electrode and 140 mL min⁻¹ · cm⁻² of synthetic air at the oxygen electrode, while SOEC measurements were performed with gas flows of 45 mL min⁻¹ · cm⁻² for H₂O and 5.6 mL min⁻¹ · cm⁻² for H₂ equivalent to a 90/10H₂O/H₂ fuel composition at the fuel electrode and 113 mL min⁻¹ · cm⁻² of synthetic air at the oxygen electrode.

Table 1

Comparison of the cell performances reported in literature for dense thin-film GDC barrier layers in SOFC and SOEC mode.

Sample	Ce _{1-x} Gd _x O ₂ , x =	Active area [cm ²]	Thickness [μm]	Deposition method	Porous air electrode	T [°C]	Current density at 0.7 V in SOFC [A · cm ²]
<i>This work</i>	0.20	1.77	0.2	Sputtering	LSCF/GDC + LSCF	750	1.82
Ref. [20]	0.20	2.01	0.2	PLD	LSCF/GDC + LSCF	750	1.50
Ref. [24]	0.10	10.0	0.3	Sputtering	LSCF/GDC + LSCF	750	1.55
Ref. [47]	0.10	0.50	1.0	Arc ion plating	LSCF-GDC	750	0.42
Ref. [49]	0.20	0.50	0.7	Sputtering	LSCF	800	1.34
Ref. [50]	0.20	1.23	0.7	Spray pyrolysis	LSCF	750	1.27
Ref. [51]	0.10	–	0.5	PLD	LSCF	800	0.90

Sample	Ce _{1-x} Gd _x O ₂ , x =	Active area [cm ²]	Thickness [μm]	Deposition method	Porous air electrode	T [°C]	Current density at 1.3 V in SOEC [A · cm ²]
<i>This work</i>	0.20	1.77	0.2	Sputtering	LSCF/GDC + LSCF	750	1.54
Ref. [48]	0.10	0.50	2.0	Sputtering	LSCF	800	1.45
Ref. [49]	0.20	0.50	0.7	Sputtering	LSCF	800	1.40
Ref. [50]	0.20	1.23	0.7	Spray pyrolysis	LSCF	750	1.75

Fig. 5. (a) Short-term degradation test on the RTP-annealed cell for 150 h at 750 °C under 1 A cm⁻² cathodic polarization in SOFC mode. (b) I-V and I-P curves before and after the durability test with corresponding Nyquist plots at 0.9 V before and after the short-term degradation test (c).

operation (see Fig. 5a), indicating an improvement of the cell

performance by + 0.3 % (equal to + ≈2.1 % kh⁻¹). The authors recently reported PLD barrier layers with long term stability (more than two years of operation) [20]. Assuming a similar stability, we carried out here short-term degradation to corroborate the evolution of the barrier layers in the first 150 h (where major degradations were previously observed). The stability of the RTP-treated cell is also confirmed by the I-V curves shown in Fig. 5b, taken before and after the 150-h test with the two curves overlapping. The fitting of the Nyquist plots acquired at 0.9 V bias (see Fig. 5c) enabled the detection of more subtle performance changes over time revealing a reduction of the total resistance (series + polarization) of about 17 %, despite a minor increase of the serial contribution (+5 mΩ cm⁻²). This early degradation test represents a strong indication of a high cell stability, which was achieved here by employing an ultrathin RTP-treated barrier layer (200 nm). As a matter of comparison, Wang et al. registered a similar behavior in the total resistance reduction (with small increase of the serial component) for a cell comprised of a 1 μm-thick dense GDC interlayer pre-sintered at 600 °C after deposition, then sintered at 1100 °C for 2 h in air and tested at 750 °C under a 0.25 A cm⁻² cathodic bias for 216 h [47]. Klemensø et al. proposed a cell configuration composed of a magnetron-sputtered doped-ceria buffer layer deposited at 450 °C with an additional spin-coated barrier layer on top sintered at 1100 °C for 4 h (≈2 μm thickness in total) with a low degradation rate of 1.3 % kh⁻¹ at 650 °C under 0.25 A · cm⁻². Overall, the doped-ceria barrier layer sintered by RTP achieved competitive performances in SOFC and SOEC mode and notable durability in fuel cell conditions with an improvement of +2.66 mV in the first 150 h.

After characterizing the sputtered GDC barrier layers on button cell level and having proven the electrochemical capabilities achievable for both RTP and oven-annealed cells, a scale-up onto large-area SOCs was performed. First, spectroscopic ellipsometry was employed to evaluate the thickness uniformity of the sputtered GDC film along the area of the cell. Fig. 6 shows the thickness map over a total area of ≈77 cm². The

Fig. 6. Thickness distribution of the RTP-annealed GDC barrier layer by magnetron sputtering on an area corresponding to a large area cell, determined by ellipsometry technique.

overall cell thickness is for over 70 % of the total area under exam ranging between 220 and 260 nm (green area). The minimum thickness is approximately 198 ± 26 nm, which is close to the targeted thickness adopted also on button cell level (ca. 200 nm). The average maximum thickness is ca. 287 ± 35 nm in the central part of the cell. The thickness gradient evaluated here is mainly intrinsic to the nature of the sputtering fabrication discussed in the experimental section (e.g. substrate-target distance, gas pressure, and static configuration with no substrate rotation).

Fig. 7. I-V curves and calculated I-P curves for the sputtered GDC barrier layers (OVEN- and RTP-annealed) integrated in large-area Ni-YSZ-supported cells (active area: 80 cm^2) and measured under fuel cell condition at three working temperatures: 750 (a), 700 (b) and 650 °C (c) in comparison with a reference cell composed of a conventional screen-printed GDC buffer layer. Horizontal lines crossing the I-V curves at 0.85 V are reported for each plot. Measurements were performed under fuel cell mode. Gas flows were equal to 2.014 L min^{-1} of $\text{H}_2 + 1.34 \text{ L min}^{-1}$ of N_2 at the fuel electrode and $37.330 \text{ L min}^{-1}$ of synthetic air at the oxygen electrode.

Characterizations of large-area cells through polarization curves measured in a short stack in fuel cell mode are reported in Fig. 7a–c for three working temperatures (750, 700, and 650 °C). The three temperatures were selected to obtain the optimal trade-off between low stack temperature-induced degradation phenomena and high stack performances. At all temperatures, OCV values are above 1.2 V, indicating proper separation of the cathodic and anodic compartments. Measurements were performed until reaching a maximum current density of 0.40 A cm^{-2} . For the short stack under exam (c.f. Fig. S2), the best-performing cell was chosen for each type of cell (oven, RTP and reference) for further discussion. For the two reference cells positioned around the five sputtered cells in the middle, the bottom one was selected due to an average improvement in electrical output at the three working temperatures of about 3.5 %. For the two RTP cells, the differences between them across all temperatures are negligible (less than 1 %), and the same applies to the three oven cells, which attest to good reproducibility in terms of barrier layer manufacture. This is illustrated in Fig. S10 of the Supporting Information, which reports the voltage achieved at 33 A (0.40 A cm^{-2}) for each cell at all working temperatures, highlighting the three cells selected for further analysis. From the polarization curves reported in Fig. 7a–c, one can see a clear improvement in the cell performance when integrating a sputtered barrier layer, the difference becomes more evident when decreasing the operation temperature. Looking at the improvement in terms of voltage percentage (%ΔV) at the maximum current density (0.4 A cm^{-2}), both the RTP and oven-annealed large-area cell voltage improvement is around 3.4 % at 750 °C and gradually increases to 6.7 % at 700 °C up to ca. 15 % at 650 °C. At constant voltage, i.e., 0.85 V, the difference is much more pronounced, the RTP large-area cell current density increases ca. 13 % at 750 °C and rises to ≈ 28 and ≈ 56 % at 700 and 650 °C, respectively.

In comparison, Coppola et al. tested similar large-area cells ($12 \times 8 \text{ cm}^2$) with a thin-film sputtered GDC protective layers using the same oxygen electrode and testing set-up achieving a similar progressive increment in terms of current density output percentage (%Δj) at a fixed voltage while lowering the temperature from 750 to 650 °C with a maximum percentage increase of 29 % at 650 °C and 0.80 V (for the best performing cell using a 300 nm-thick GDC oven-annealed barrier layer, current density $\approx 0.35 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$) in comparison to a similar reference cell with screen-printed GDC [52]. This is lower than the improvement at the same temperature and voltage obtained by the RTP-annealed large-area cell discussed in this work (current density 0.40 A cm^{-2}), which gives nearly a 60 % improvement, leading to better performance at all three working temperatures with respect to the sputtered GDC cells measured in ref. [52].

The different impact of the barrier layer with temperature indicates a thermally activated effect likely related to a change of the limiting phenomena when using the barrier layers studied here. One possibility is given by a difference in the activation energy for ionic conduction between the materials effectively present in the two types of cells. In Fig. S11 are reported the Arrhenius plots of the total area-specific resistance extracted from the polarization curves (c.f. Fig. 7) in the activation region (at 0.9 V), disclosing an increase of the activation energy for the reference cell with respect to the RTP-treated one. In the case of the sputtered barrier layer, the SEM image and the nano-XRF characterization showed strong barrier layer integrity, similar to what already observed for PLD barrier layers [17]. However, the reference cells show altered interfaces with the presence of Gd-rich YSZ, intermixed YSZ-GDC, and Sr-depleted LSCF regions. The resulting composition from the cationic intermixing are characterized by lower ionic conductivity and higher activation energy [13,53,54], resulting in a more substantial impact on the performance at lower temperatures. One can note that the performance and the improvement obtained at the large-area cell level tested in short-stack configuration is lower than the one obtained at the button cell level. Indeed, at 0.85 V (a lower working voltage, e.g. 0.7 V, was not reached with the short stack), the RTP large-area cell current density increase is ca. 13 % at 750 °C which is

notably lower than the improvement obtained at button cell level at the same temperature and voltage of about 41 % (c.f. Fig. 4a). Moreover, the current density at 0.85 V is more than twice as high in the button cell compared to the large-area cell measured in the preliminary electrochemical study, increasing from 0.42 to 0.88 A cm⁻². The same tendency was observed in our previous work on up-scaling the PLD barrier layer [17] and can be associated with several factors: the increase of active area [55], the presence of additional components such as interconnects in short-stack configuration, the different test rigs and the different testing conditions. Overall, the use of RF magnetron sputtering and RTP for the fabrication and annealing of barrier layers for large-area cells appears to be feasible, allowing a notable increase in cell performance in SOFC operation mode.

The short-stack (cf. Fig. S2) discussed above was eventually tested in electrolysis mode at 750, 700 and 650 °C with a fuel gas composition composed of 90 vol% H₂O + 10 vol% H₂. The results are reported in Fig. 8a–c, showing the performances of the same selected cells discussed above (cf. Fig. 7). The OCV values for all cells progressively increase from approximately 0.85 to 0.87 and 0.90 V at 750, 700 and 650 °C, respectively. These values are in good agreement with the expected OCV calculated considering a 90/10H₂O/H₂ fuel ratio [56]. At a fixed operating voltage of 1.3 V, the improvement given by the RTP-annealed cell with respect to the reference in terms of electrolysis current increases from ca. 8 % at 750 °C to ≈22 and ≈ 28 % at 700 and 650 °C, respectively. Electrolysis currents at operational voltage (1.3 V) reached by the RTP-treated cell are: 0.75, 0.60, and 0.35 A cm⁻² at 750, 700, and 600 °C, respectively. These results obtained are aligned with other Ni-YSZ-supported large-area cells (with active area: 48 cm²) measured in a short stack in electrolysis mode with a 90/10H₂O/H₂ fuel ratio [57].

This study validates the hypothesis that RTP annealing can be successfully introduced in large-area SOCs manufacturing to achieve electrical outputs and stability equal to conventional oven annealing while reducing the overall production time and energy consumption. For high-temperature thin-film production methods such as PLD, doped-ceria buffer layers have been reported to function effectively as protective interlayers even without an additional annealing step [58]. On the other hand, for more scalable approaches, such as magnetron sputtering under room-temperature conditions, a post-fabrication annealing step is essential. According to our estimations, the use of magnetron sputtering combined with RTP will reduce the energy consumption by approximately 15 % per kW · h of SOC produced and lower the production time by ca. 50 % per cell produced by RTP compared to conventional oven annealing.

4. Conclusions

Scalable and energy-efficient fabrication of highly performing solid oxide cells (SOCs) was presented by developing efficient diffusion barrier layers based on RTP annealing of 200 nm-thick GDC barrier layer produced by room-temperature large-area magnetron sputtering. This study compared RTP and conventional oven-annealed diffusion layers, revealing no significant structural or morphological differences. Nano-XRF analysis identified small, isolated SrZrO₃ grains that did not affect cell performance. Electrochemical tests using Ni-YSZ-supported commercial button cells demonstrated a 40 % improvement in both SOFC and SOEC performance compared to a reference cell with a screen-printed oven-annealed barrier layer. Furthermore, cells were tested for 150 h at a high cathodic current density (1 A cm⁻²), showing an apparent improvement of +2.66 mV. Even more significantly, we successfully scaled up and annealed the sputtered layer to large-area and measured it in a short stack configuration showing an improvement of up to 60 % and 28 % at 650 °C in SOFC and SOEC mode, respectively, compared to the reference large-area cell, highlighting the viability of the RTP approach. The electrical output achieved on both small- and large-scale was comparable to the cells with GDC interlayer annealed in a conventional oven. We successfully demonstrated that RTP, integrated

Fig. 8. I-V curves for the sputtered GDC barrier layers (OVEN- and RTP-annealed) integrated in large-area Ni-YSZ-supported cells (active area: 80 cm²) and measured under electrolysis condition at three working temperatures: 750 (a), 700 (b) and 650 °C (c) in comparison with a reference cell composed of a conventional screen-printed GDC buffer layer. Horizontal lines crossing the I-V curves at 1.3 V are reported for each plot. Measurements were performed under fuel cell mode. Gas flows were equal to 0.436 L min⁻¹ of H₂ and 3.918 L min⁻¹ of H₂O at the fuel electrode and 4.083 L min⁻¹ of synthetic air at the oxygen electrode.

into this fabrication route, lowers energy consumption per cell by 15 % and fabrication time per part produced by approximately 50 %. Combined with the low-energy, scalable room-temperature magnetron sputtering deposition of dense, thin GDC protective interlayers, this approach offers a promising, fast, cost- and energy-efficient solution for industrial-scale SOC production.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Florelo Buzi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lucile Bernadet:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Jordi Orrit-Prat:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Raül Bonet:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Jaume Caro:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Dario Montinaro:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Jan Pieter Ouweltjes:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Federico Baiutti:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Marc Torrell:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Alex Morata:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Albert Tarancón:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.237629>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- M.B. Mogensen, M. Chen, H.L. Frandsen, C. Graves, J.B. Hansen, K.V. Hansen, A. Hauch, T. Jacobsen, S.H. Jensen, T.L. Skafte, X. Sun, Reversible solid-oxide cells for clean and sustainable energy, *Clean Energy* 3 (3) (2019) 175–201, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ce/zkz023>.
- S. He, Y. Zou, K. Chen, S.P. Jiang, A critical review of key materials and issues in solid oxide cells, *Interdiscip. Mater.* 2 (1) (2023) 111–136, <https://doi.org/10.1002/idm2.12068>.
- N. Mahato, A. Banerjee, A. Gupta, S. Omar, K. Balani, Progress in material selection for solid oxide fuel cell technology: a review, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 72 (2015) 141–337, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2015.01.001>.
- M.S. Khan, X. Xu, R. Knibbe, Z. Zhu, Air electrodes and related degradation mechanisms in solid oxide electrolysis and reversible solid oxide cells, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 143 (2021) 110918, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.110918>.
- J. Wang, Z. Yang, K. Yang, S. Peng, Kinetics of oxygen reaction in porous La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8}O_{3-δ}-Ce_{0.8}Gd_{0.2}O_{1.9} composite electrodes for solid oxide cells, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 46 (50) (2021) 25608–25619, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.05.071>.
- A. Chen, G. Bourne, K. Siebein, R. DeHoff, E. Wachsman, K. Jones, Characterization of lanthanum zirconate formation at the A-site-deficient strontium-doped lanthanum manganite Cathode/Yttrium-Stabilized zirconia electrolyte interface of solid oxide fuel cells, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 91 (8) (2008) 2670–2675, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1551-2916.2008.02524.x>.
- J. Laurencin, M. Hubert, D.F. Sanchez, S. Pylpko, M. Morales, A. Morata, B. Morel, D. Montinaro, F. Lefebvre-Joud, E. Siebert, Degradation Mechanism of La 0.6 Sr 0.4 Co 0.2 Fe 0.8 O 3-δ /Gd 0.1 Ce 0.9 O 2-δ Composite Electrode Operated under Solid Oxide Electrolysis and Fuel Cell Conditions, *Electrochim. Acta* 241 (2017) 459–476, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2017.05.011>.
- J.C. De Vero, K. Develos-Bagarinao, H. Matsuda, H. Kishimoto, T. Ishiyama, K. Yamaji, T. Horita, H. Yokokawa, Sr and Zr transport in PLD-grown Gd-Doped ceria interlayers, *Solid State Ionics* 314 (2018) 165–171, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssi.2017.10.023>.
- K. Crossley, D. Montinaro, Insights into strontium zirconate-induced interface pressures in solid oxide electrolysis cells, *J. Power Sources* 589 (2024) 233747, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2023.233747>.
- A. Tsoga, A. Gupta, A. Naoumidis, P. Nikolopoulos, Gadolinia-doped ceria and yttria stabilized zirconia interfaces: regarding their application for SOFC technology, *Acta Mater.* 48 (18–19) (2000) 4709–4714, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-6454\(00\)00261-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-6454(00)00261-5).
- T. Klemens, J. Nielsen, P. Blennow, Å.H. Persson, T. Stegk, B.H. Christensen, S. Sønderby, High performance metal-supported solid oxide fuel cells with Gd-Doped ceria barrier layers, *J. Power Sources* 196 (22) (2011) 9459–9466, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2011.07.014>.
- I. Jang, S. Kim, C. Kim, H. Lee, H. Yoon, T. Song, U. Paik, Interface engineering of yttrium stabilized zirconia/gadolinium doped ceria Bi-Layer electrolyte solid oxide fuel cell for boosting electrochemical performance, *J. Power Sources* 435 (2019) 226776, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2019.226776>.
- T. Matsui, S. Li, H. Muroyama, K. Kishida, H. Inui, K. Eguchi, Electrochemical property of solid solutions formed in (La,Sr)(Co,Fe)O₃– Cathode/Doped-CeO₂ Interlayer/Y₂O₃-ZrO₂ electrolyte system during operation of solid oxide fuel cells, *Solid State Ionics* 300 (2017) 135–139, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssi.2016.12.014>.
- J. Szász, F. Wankmüller, V. Wilde, H. Störmer, D. Gerthsen, N.H. Menzler, E. Ivers-Tiffée, Nature and functionality of La_{0.58}Sr_{0.4}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8}O_{3-δ}/Gd_{0.2}Ce_{0.8}O_{2-δ}/Y_{0.16}Zr_{0.84}O_{2-δ} interfaces in SOFCs, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 165 (10) (2018) F898–F906, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0031811jes>.
- M. Morales, A. Pesce, A. Slodczyk, M. Torrell, P. Piccardo, D. Montinaro, A. Tarancón, A. Morata, Enhanced performance of gadolinia-doped ceria diffusion barrier layers fabricated by pulsed laser deposition for large-area solid oxide fuel cells, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* 1 (5) (2018) 1955–1964, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.8b00039>.
- M. Morales, V. Miguel-Pérez, A. Tarancón, A. Slodczyk, M. Torrell, B. Ballesteros, J. P. Ouweltjes, J.M. Bassat, D. Montinaro, A. Morata, Multi-scale analysis of the diffusion barrier layer of gadolinia-doped ceria in a solid oxide fuel cell operated in a stack for 3000 h, *J. Power Sources* 344 (2017) 141–151, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.01.109>.
- L. Bernadet, J. Segura-Ruiz, L. Yedra, S. Estrade, F. Peiró, D. Montinaro, M. Torrell, A. Morata, A. Tarancón, Enhanced diffusion barrier layers for avoiding degradation in SOFCs aged for 14000 h during 2 years, *J. Power Sources* 555 (2023) 232400, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2022.232400>.
- Q. Bai, K. Develos-Bagarinao, T. Yamaguchi, T. Yamaguchi, H. Kishimoto, Unraveling the pivotal role of heterointerfaces on oxide ion transport in solid oxide fuel cells, *J. Power Sources* 593 (2024) 233952, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2023.233952>.
- M. Machado, F. Baiutti, L. Bernadet, A. Morata, M. Nuñez, J.P. Ouweltjes, F. C. Fonseca, M. Torrell, A. Tarancón, Functional thin films as cathode/electrolyte interlayers: a strategy to enhance the performance and durability of solid oxide fuel cells, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 10 (33) (2022) 17317–17325, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2TA03641J>.
- L. Bernadet, F. Buzi, F. Baiutti, J. Segura-Ruiz, J. Dolado, D. Montinaro, M. Torrell, A. Morata, A. Tarancón, Thickness effect of thin-film barrier layers for enhanced long-term operation of solid oxide fuel cells, *APL Energy* 1 (3) (2023) 036101, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0159765>.
- M. Riegraf, F. Han, N. Sata, R. Costa, Intercalation of thin-film Gd-Doped ceria barrier layers in electrolyte-supported solid oxide cells: physicochemical aspects, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 13 (31) (2021) 37239–37251, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaami.1c11175>.
- F. Han, M. Lang, P. Szabo, C. Geipel, C. Walter, R. Costa, Performance and degradation of electrolyte supported SOECs with advanced thin-film gadolinium doped ceria barrier layers in long-term stack test, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 171 (5) (2024) 054515, <https://doi.org/10.1149/1945-7111/ad4781>.
- S. Sønderby, P.L. Poppa, J. Lu, B.H. Christensen, K.P. Almqvist, L.P. Nielsen, P. Eklund, Strontium diffusion in magnetron sputtered gadolinia-doped ceria thin film barrier coatings for solid oxide fuel cells, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 3 (7) (2013) 923–929, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201300003>.
- N. Coppola, P. Polverino, G. Carapella, C. Sacco, A. Galdi, D. Montinaro, L. Maritato, C. Pianese, Optimization of the electrical performances in solid oxide fuel cells with room temperature sputter deposited Gd_{0.1}Ce_{0.9}O_{1.95} buffer layers by controlling their granularity via the in-Air annealing step, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 45 (23) (2020) 12997–13008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.02.187>.
- M. Mickan, P. Coddet, J. Vulliet, A. Caillard, T. Sauvage, A.-L. Thomann, Optimized magnetron sputtering process for the deposition of gadolinia doped ceria layers with controlled structural properties, *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 398 (2020) 126095, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2020.126095>.
- Y. Yang, Y. Zhang, M. Yan, A review on the preparation of thin-film YSZ electrolyte of SOFCs by magnetron sputtering technology, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 298 (2022) 121627, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2022.121627>.
- J. Liang, Q. Liu, T. Li, Y. Luo, S. Lu, X. Shi, F. Zhang, A.M. Asiri, X. Sun, Magnetron sputtering enabled sustainable synthesis of nanomaterials for energy electrocatalysis, *Green Chem.* 23 (8) (2021) 2834–2867, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0GC03994B>.
- J.T. Gudmundsson, Physics and technology of magnetron sputtering discharges, *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* 29 (11) (2020) 113001, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6595/abb7bd>.

- [29] K. Rodrigo, S. Heiroth, N. Pryds, L. Theil Kuhn, V. Esposito, S. Linderth, J. Schou, T. Lippert, The effects of thermal annealing on the structure and the electrical transport properties of ultrathin gadolinia-doped ceria films grown by pulsed laser deposition, *Appl. Phys. A* 104 (3) (2011) 845–850, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-011-6424-y>.
- [30] F. Roozeboom, N. Parekh, Rapid thermal processing systems: a review with emphasis on temperature control, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. B Microelectron. Process. Phenom.* 8 (6) (1990) 1249–1259, <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.584902>.
- [31] V.Y. Kireev, A.S. Tsimbalov, Rapid thermal processing: a new step forward in microelectronics technologies, *RAPID Therm. Process.* 30 (4) (2001).
- [32] W.S. Scheld, S. Lobe, C. Dellen, M. Ihrig, G. Häuschen, L.C. Hoff, M. Finsterbusch, S. Uhlenbruck, O. Guillon, D. Fattakhova-Rohlfing, Rapid thermal processing of garnet-based composite cathodes, *J. Power Sources* 545 (2022) 231872, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2022.231872>.
- [33] O. Guillon, W. Rheinheimer, M. Bram, A perspective on emerging and future sintering technologies of ceramic materials, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* 25 (18) (2023) 2201870, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.202201870>.
- [34] R. Singh, Rapid isothermal processing, *J. Appl. Phys.* 63 (8) (1988) R59–R114, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.340176>.
- [35] F. Monaco, M. Hubert, J. Vuillet, J.P. Ouweltjes, D. Montinaro, P. Cloetens, P. Piccardo, F. Lefebvre-Joud, J. Laurencin, Degradation of Ni-YSZ electrodes in solid oxide cells: impact of polarization and initial microstructure on the Ni evolution, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 166 (15) (2019) F1229–F1242, <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.21261915jes>.
- [36] J.-S. Shin, M. Saqib, M. Jo, K. Park, K.M. Park, J.S. Ahn, H.-T. Lim, J.-Y. Park, Degradation mechanisms of solid oxide fuel cells under various thermal cycling conditions, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 13 (42) (2021) 49868–49878, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.1c13779>.
- [37] M. Perz, E. Bucher, C. Gspan, J. Waldhäusl, F. Hofer, W. Sitte, Long-term degradation of La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8}O_{3-δ} IT-SOFC cathodes due to silicon poisoning, *Solid State Ionics* 288 (2016) 22–27, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssi.2016.01.005>.
- [38] N. Ni, C.C. Wang, S.P. Jiang, S.J. Skinner, Synergistic Effects of Temperature and Polarization on Cr Poisoning of La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8}O_{3-δ} Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Cathodes, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 7 (15) (2019) 9253–9262, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9TA01275C>.
- [39] J. Villanova, S. Schlabach, A. Brisse, A. Léon, X-Ray fluorescence nano-imaging of long-term operated solid oxide electrolysis cells, *J. Power Sources* 421 (2019) 100–108, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2019.02.084>.
- [40] G. Martínez-Criado, J. Villanova, R. Tucoulou, D. Salomon, J.-P. Suuronen, S. Labouré, C. Guilloud, V. Valls, R. Barrett, E. Gagliardini, Y. Dabin, R. Baker, S. Bohic, C. Cohen, J. Morse, ID16B: a hard X-Ray nanoprobe beamline at the ESRF for nano-analysis, *J. Synchrotron Radiat.* 23 (1) (2016) 344–352, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600577515019839>.
- [41] L. Chen, P. Fleming, V. Morris, J.D. Holmes, M.A. Morris, Size-related lattice parameter changes and surface defects in ceria nanocrystals, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 114 (30) (2010) 12909–12919, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp1031465>.
- [42] A. Arabaci, M.F. Öksüzömer, Preparation and characterization of 10mol% Gd doped CeO₂ (GDC) electrolyte for SOFC applications, *Ceram. Int.* 38 (8) (2012) 6509–6515, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2012.05.030>.
- [43] C. Artini, M. Pani, M.M. Carnasciali, M.T. Buscaglia, J.R. Plaisier, G.A. Costa, Structural features of Sm- and Gd-Doped ceria studied by synchrotron X-Ray diffraction and μ -Raman spectroscopy, *Inorg. Chem.* 54 (8) (2015) 4126–4137, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.5b00395>.
- [44] D.-J. Kim, Lattice parameters, ionic conductivities, and solubility limits in fluorite-structure MO₂ oxide [M = Hf⁴⁺, Zr⁴⁺, Ce⁴⁺, Th⁴⁺, U⁴⁺] solid solutions, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 72 (8) (1989) 1415–1421, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1989.tb07663.x>.
- [45] R.W. Cairns, E. Ott, X-Ray studies of the system nickel—oxygen—water. I. Nickelous oxide and Hydroxide¹, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 55 (2) (1933) 527–533, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja01329a013>.
- [46] A. Mai, V.A.C. Haanappel, S. Uhlenbruck, F. Tietz, D. Stöver, Ferrite-based perovskites as cathode materials for anode-supported solid oxide fuel cells, *Solid State Ionics* 176 (15–16) (2005) 1341–1350, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssi.2005.03.009>.
- [47] Y. Wang, C. Jia, Z. Lyu, M. Han, J. Wu, Z. Sun, F. Iguchi, K. Yashiro, T. Kawada, Performance and stability analysis of SOFC containing thin and dense gadolinium-doped ceria interlayer sintered at low temperature, *J. Materiomics* 8 (2) (2022) 347–357, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmat.2021.09.001>.
- [48] S.J. Kim, S.W. Kim, Y.M. Park, K.J. Kim, G.M. Choi, Effect of Gd-Doped ceria interlayer on the stability of solid oxide electrolysis cell, *Solid State Ionics* 295 (2016) 25–31, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssi.2016.07.007>.
- [49] P. Coddet, M.-L. Amany, J. Vuillet, A. Caillard, A.-L. Thomann, YSZ/GDC bilayer and gradient barrier layers deposited by reactive magnetron sputtering for solid oxide cells, *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 357 (2019) 103–113, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2018.09.085>.
- [50] S. Molin, J. Karczewski, B. Kamecki, A. Mroziński, S.-F. Wang, P. Jasiński, Processing of Ce_{0.8}Gd_{0.2}O_{2-δ} barrier layers for solid oxide cells: the effect of preparation method and thickness on the interdiffusion and electrochemical performance, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 40 (15) (2020) 5626–5633, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2020.06.006>.
- [51] G. Nurk, M. Vestli, P. Möller, R. Jaaniso, M. Kodu, H. Mändar, T. Romann, R. Kanarbik, E. Lust, Mobility of Sr in gadolinia doped ceria barrier layers prepared using spray pyrolysis, pulsed laser deposition and magnetron sputtering methods, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 163 (2) (2016) F88–F96, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0531602jes>.
- [52] N. Coppola, H.S. Ur Rehman, G. Carapella, P. Polverino, D. Montinaro, F. Martinelli, V. Granata, A. Galdi, L. Maritato, C. Pianese, Large area solid oxide fuel cells with room temperature sputtered barrier layers: role of the layer thickness and uniformity in the enhancement of the electrochemical performances and durability, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 48 (77) (2023) 30120–30131, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.04.170>.
- [53] T. Matsui, S. Li, Y. Inoue, N. Yoshida, H. Muroyama, K. Eguchi, Degradation analysis of solid oxide fuel cells with (La,Sr)(Co,Fe)O_{3-δ} Cathode/Gd₂O₃-CeO₂ Interlayer/Y₂O₃-ZrO₂ electrolyte system: the influences of microstructural change and solid solution formation, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 166 (4) (2019) F295–F300, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0841904jes>.
- [54] S.P. Jiang, Development of lanthanum strontium cobalt ferrite perovskite electrodes of solid oxide fuel cells – a review, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 44 (14) (2019) 7448–7493, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.01.212>.
- [55] H. Sumi, H. Shimada, Y. Yamaguchi, K. Nomura, K. Sato, Why is the performance different between Small- and large-scale SOFCs? *Electrochim. Acta* 443 (2023) 141965, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2023.141965>.
- [56] M. Lang, C. Bohn, K. Couturier, X. Sun, S.J. McPhail, T. Malkow, A. Pilenga, Q. Fu, Q. Liu, Electrochemical quality assurance of solid oxide electrolyser (SOEC) stacks, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 166 (15) (2019) F1180–F1189, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0041915jes>.
- [57] G. Rinaldi, S. Diethelm, E. Oveisi, P. Burdet, J. Van Herle, D. Montinaro, Q. Fu, A. Brisse, Post-test analysis on a solid oxide cell stack operated for 10,700 hours in steam electrolysis mode, *Fuel Cells* 17 (4) (2017) 541–549, <https://doi.org/10.1002/fuce.201600194>.
- [58] F. Buzi, K. Kreka, J. Santiso, L. Rapenne, Z. Sha, J.O. Douglas, F. Chiabrera, A. Morata, M. Burriel, S. Skinner, L. Bernadet, F. Baiutti, A. Tarancón, A self-assembled multiphase thin film as an oxygen electrode for enhanced durability in reversible solid oxide cells, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 16 (33) (2024) 43462–43473, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.4c06290>.